

1 **The effects of headspace volume reactor on the microbial**
2 **community structure during fermentation processes for**
3 **volatile fatty acid production**

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22 **Abstract**

23 The transition from traditional wastewater treatment plants to biorefineries represents an
24 environmentally and economically sustainable approach to extracting valuable compounds from
25 waste. Sewage sludge produced from wastewater treatment is incinerated or disposed of in specific
26 landfills. Repurposing this waste material to recover valuable resources could help lower disposal
27 costs and reduce environmental impact by producing other beneficial polymers. Microorganisms
28 present in the sewage sludge can ferment organic pollutants, producing volatile fatty acids (VFA),
29 precursors for biopolymers that could be used as an alternative to petroleum-derived plastics. To
30 boost VFA production during sewage sludge fermentation, it is necessary to understand the operating
31 microbial community and its metabolic capacities in anaerobic conditions. This study presents the
32 influence of the headspace volume on the microbial community and the VFA production to define
33 the best operational parameters in a 225 L pilot plant fermenter. The wasted sewage sludge was
34 withdrawn from an Oxidative Settling Anaerobic plant that collected wastewater from the canteen and
35 dormitory of the UNIPA Campus (Palermo University, Italy) and incubated using a 40% and a 60%
36 headspace volume. The microbial community was analysed before and after the fermentation process
37 through metataxonomic analysis, and VFA yields were determined by gas-chromatography analysis.
38 Our results showed that the 40% headspace volume induced a 10-fold higher VFA production than
39 the 60% headspace volume, modulating the microbial community's efforts to establish a VFA-
40 producing factory. Notably, at 40% headspace, the relative abundance of bacteria, like Proteobacteria,
41 Firmicutes, Actinobacteria, and Chloroflexi, significantly increased, as well as the relative abundance
42 of Bacteroidetes and Verrucomicrobia decreased during the fermentation process. This result is
43 consistent with the selection of efficient VFA-producing bacteria that lead to increased VFA yields
44 that are not obtained at 60% headspace. Thus, reducing headspace is a promising strategy that can be
45 implemented, even in full-scale plants, to optimize the wastewater reuse process and maximize VFA
46 production to produce bioplastics, like polyhydroxyalkanoate, for the transition from linear
47 wastewater treatment plants to circular biorefineries.

48 **Keywords:** Acidogenic fermentation; Headspace; Metataxonomic analyses; Volatile fatty acids.

49 **1. Introduction**

50 Sewage sludge (SS) production at wastewater treatment plants has significantly increased in
51 recent years due to intensified industrial activity and enlarged population growth (Bianchini et
52 al., 2016). Traditional methods of SS management, such as landfilling and incineration, have a
53 high environmental impact and cost (Hao et al., 2020). The introduction of circular economy
54 approaches can offer a sustainable alternative, treating SS as a resource rather than waste
55 (Mannina et al., 2021). SS can be further exploited to produce valuable nutrients and organic
56 compounds through anaerobic digestion. This process involves the microbial decomposition of
57 organic matter through stages such as hydrolysis, acidogenesis, acetogenesis, and
58 methanogenesis, ultimately yielding methane (CH₄) and carbon dioxide (CO₂). The production of
59 high-value-added compounds such as volatile fatty acids (VFAs) can be increased by inhibiting
60 certain stages, particularly acetogenesis and methanogenesis. VFAs are biochemical building
61 blocks that microorganisms can use as substrates to produce several biopolymers. Despite the
62 potential of this method, challenges persist, particularly in optimising VFA production and
63 organic matter conversion. Various pre-treatments have been explored to assess factors like
64 hydraulic retention time, temperature, pH, nutrient availability, and headspace pressure (HP), with
65 studies indicating that lower HP promotes VFA production (Koch et al., 2015; García-Depraect
66 et al., 2022; Darvekar et al., 2019; Li et al., 2019; Mineo et al., 2023). Although bacterial and
67 archaeal species have an essential role in VFA yields and many environmental factors influence
68 microbial fermentation (Zhang et al., 2020; Di Leto et al., 2022; Mineo et al., 2024; Di Leto et
69 al., 2024), research on the influence of microbial communities on fermentation and VFA
70 production is still in its early stages.

71 Previous studies have shown a positive correlation between reduced headspace volume and
72 increased VFA production (Xu et al., 2020). Li et al. (2019) assessed how headspace affects VFA
73 production from proteins and discovered that lower headspace pressure enhances VFA
74 production. Headspace can have several impacts on anaerobic sewage sludge fermentation:
75 reducing headspace can create an environment in which acidogenic bacteria can exploit H₂ and
76 CO₂ to produce VFA (Yan et al., 2014). Headspace is also important to avoid pressure buildup
77 during methane production, which reduces VFA production (Abubakar et al., 2024). Indeed,
78 Mineo et al. 2023 demonstrated that a 40% headspace volume induced a 10-fold higher VFA
79 production than a 60% headspace volume. However, none of these studies have prioritized the
80 analysis of the sewage sludge microbiota structure, which is crucial in acidogenic fermentation
81 and primarily responsible for VFA production. As far as the authors know, reports have yet to
82 examine the microbial community of fermented sewage sludge under controlled headspace to

83 implement VFA production. This study aims to fill this gap by examining the microbial
84 community of fermentation sludge samples under different headspace volumes and comparing
85 them with their initial compositions. The prokaryotic microbiota structure was examined using
86 metataxonomic analyses to identify bacteria involved in acidogenic fermentation, focusing on
87 controlling headspace volume to increase VFA yields that can be used for the production of
88 bioplastics, like polyhydroxyalkanoate during microbial fermentation (Di Leto et al., 2022).

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91 **2. Materials and methods**

92 **2.1 Experimental setup**

93 The fermentation experiments were carried out at Palermo University, Italy's Water Resource
94 Recovery Facility (Mannina et al., 2021). The fermentation unit is located in the
95 polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) production line of the pilot plant hall and was previously described by
96 Mineo et al. (2023). It consists of a continuous stirred tank fermenter (total volume of 225 L) fed with
97 the sewage sludge produced by the wastewater treatment plant of the pilot plant hall and equipped
98 with sampling ports for liquid and gas samples (Figure 1). The fermenter is linked to an ultra-filtration
99 (UF) unit (total volume of 43 L) equipping a hollow fiber membrane (polyvinylidene, 0.03- μ m
100 porosity and 1.4-m² surface area). Once the fermentation process was completed, the sewage sludge
101 was pumped to the UF unit and filtered with a net flow rate of 13.2 L/h. The UF unit has a gas
102 recycling pump (Gilian GilAir Plus, Recom Industriale), reducing membrane fouling during the
103 sludge's filtration while keeping the anaerobic environment. The fermenter was operated with a
104 hydraulic and sludge retention time of 5 days.

105 The SS was collected in two seasons (F1, winter and F2, spring) from the wastewater treatment line
106 within the pilot plant, which adopts an oxic-settling-anaerobic (OSA) configuration. Two
107 fermentation experiments were started: fermentation 1, with 40% of the SS and 60% of the headspace,
108 while fermentation 2, with 60% of the SS and 40% of the headspace. Throughout the fermentation,
109 pH, temperature and Oxidation Reduction Potential (ORP) were continuously monitored inside the
110 fermenter by using WiFi - Multi 3630 IDS "WTW" (Xylem brand) and related probes. Other
111 parameters, such as total chemical oxygen demand (tCOD), soluble chemical oxygen demand
112 (sCOD), soluble proteins and carbohydrates, ammonium (NH₄-N), orthophosphate (PO₄-P), and
113 volatile fatty acids (VFAs) were measured at the beginning and end of the fermentation process, as
114 well as during the VFA peak day, following the procedure outlined in Table 1 and detailed in Mineo
115 et al., 2023. Samples were collected at the start and end of the fermentation process to conduct
116 metataxonomic analyses.

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123 **Figure 1.** Schematic view of the fermentation unit. It consists of a fermenter, an ultrafiltration unit,
124 and a tank for collecting the permeate. The scheme also shows the pH, temperature, ORP probes, the
125 three connected pumps, and the gas recirculation pump.

126 2.2 Analytical methods

127 Standard methods were applied for sCOD, TSS, VSS, EPS, SMP, NH₄-N, and PO₄-P analysis
128 (APHA, 2012). VFAs were measured by treating filtered sludge samples used for sCOD analysis with
129 dimethyl carbonate (DMC), according to Ghidotti et al. (2018). Briefly, SS samples were filtered
130 using 0.45 µm filters and mixed with 1 mL of DMC and 0.1 mL of a saturated potassium bisulfate
131 (KHSO₄) solution. The mixture was then centrifuged at 1700 rcf for 10 minutes. An Agilent
132 Technologies 7820A gas chromatograph (GC) equipped with a flame ionization detector (FID) and a
133 DB FFAA column (30 m × 0.25 × mm × 0.25 µm) was used to determine the VFA concentration
134 (Montiel-Jarillo, 2021).

135

136 2.3 Prokaryotic Microbiota Structure Analysis

137 The prokaryotic microbiota structure of SS was analysed by metataxonomic analysis based on next-
138 generation sequencing (NGS) of the 16S rDNA gene amplicons obtained from metagenomic DNA.
139 In particular, four SS samples were analysed. T0-F1 and T0-F2 correspond to the starting SS of
140 fermentation experiments 1 and 2, respectively (F1 and F2); TF-F1 and TF-F2 were the samples
141 collected after fermentation of experiments 1 and 2, respectively. The analyses were performed on
142 unfiltered and uncentrifuged samples. The procedures already described (Presti et al., 2021; Di Leto
143 et al., 2024) were followed. The DNA extractions were evaluated by 1% (w/v) agarose gel
144 electrophoresis analysis, adding 0.5 µg/mL ethidium bromide for visualisation using a UV lamp. The
145 concentrations of the DNA, extracted from 1 g of SS samples and the corresponding tenfold serial
146 dilutions, were measured by reading absorbance at 260 nm with a NanoDrop 2000c
147 spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA). The purity of the extracted DNA
148 was evaluated by measuring the absorbance ratios (260/280 and 260/230 nm) to indicate
149 contamination due to proteins and organic compounds or chaotropic agents, respectively. PCR of the
150 16S rDNA gene was carried out with the parameters and primers described in Di Leto et al., 2024.
151 Amplification products were sequenced in one 300 bp paired-end run on an Illumina MiSeq platform
152 at BMR Genomics (Padova, Italy). The raw 16S rDNA data were processed using the QIIME2
153 software (<https://qiime2.org/>) as paired-end sequences. The denoising approach processed
154 overlapping paired-end reads with the plugin DADA2. Unique amplicon sequence variants (ASVs)
155 were assigned and aligned to the Greengenes reference database at 99% sequence similarity
156 (<https://greengenes.secondgenome.com/>). The number of ASVs and the percentages of relative
157 abundances of phyla, orders, classes, and families were determined for each sample. In particular,
158 183804 high-quality reads filtered from the 257188 raw reads were obtained. HeatMap generation
159 was conducted via the online web server (<http://heatmapper.ca/expression/>), employing a "complete
160 linkage" calculation based on Pearson correlation and focusing on families. METAGENassist
161 (<http://www.metagenassist.ca>), accessed on 5 March 2024, was used to distinguish the microbial
162 species based on their metabolic activity.

163 **3. Results and Discussion**

164 **3.1. sCOD, nutrients, and VFA production**

165 Two fermentation experiments were carried out at the Water Resource Recovery Facility at Palermo
166 University in Italy using the SS collected in two different seasons (F1, winter and F2, spring) from
167 the wastewater treatment line within the pilot plant, which adopts an oxic-settling-anaerobic (OSA)
168 configuration. Fermentation 1 was filled up with 40% of the SS, leaving 60% of the headspace, while

169 fermentation 2, with 60% of the SS, led 40% of the headspace. Samples were collected and analysed
 170 for chemical properties on the first day of the fermentation (T0), on the peak day of sCOD (TP) that
 171 was after 11 days, and on the final day (TF), after 20 days of fermentation (Table 1). Different
 172 headspace volumes provoked a different sCOD production being 4-fold higher sCOD production
 173 (615mg/L) in F2 than in F1 (146mg/L), although at the beginning of the fermentations (T0), the sCOD
 174 production was 2.6-fold higher in F1 (99mg/L) than in F2 (37mg/L). Previous studies (Zuo et al.,
 175 2020) state that sCOD and VFA generally assume the same trend after fermentation. In fact, in this
 176 work, during fermentation in F2, the increased sCOD value is associated with an increase in VFA
 177 yield. Ammonium was found 4, 13 and 11-fold higher in T0, TP, and TF of F2 than F1, while
 178 orthophosphates were approximately the same in the two fermentations at T0 (6.1 mg P/L in F1 and
 179 5.21 mg P/L in F2) and were found 1.18 and 1.13 -fold higher in TP and TF of F2 than F1. Typically,
 180 increased values of ammonium and orthophosphate in fermentation with increased VFA production
 181 are the result of accelerated degradation of proteins and other biomolecules containing nitrogen and
 182 phosphorus, likely to be due to microbial metabolic activity (Vijande et al., 2024). The two
 183 fermentations had a similar content of soluble proteins, and while carbohydrates proteins were found
 184 1.16 and 1.37 -fold higher in T0 and TF of F2 than F1; carbohydrates were found 1.40 and 1.92 -fold
 185 higher in T0 and TF of F2 than F1. According to Mineo et al., 2023, these results suggest an effective
 186 higher protein hydrolysis during F2. In the TP, the VFA yield was 6.6-fold higher in the F2
 187 experiment (197.76 mg COD/L) than in F1 (29.63 mg COD/L). Thus, headspace volume affected the
 188 fermentation process and the VFA rate.

189 **Table 1.** Features of the analysed SS samples in the T0 (starting day), TP (VFA peak day), and TF
 190 (final day): sCOD (soluble chemical oxygen demand), tCOD (total oxygen demand), chemical
 191 oxygen demand solubilisation, ammonium, orthophosphate, soluble proteins and carbohydrates,
 192 volatile fatty acid (VFA) and VFA/sCOD ratio.

Parameter	Unit	T0		TP		TF	
		F1	F2	F1	F2	F1	F2
sCOD	mg/L	99	37	146	615	133	475
tCOD	mg/L	7340	4801	-	-	5933	2948
COD solubilization	%	-	-	0.84	12.04	0.67	9.12

Ammonium	mg N/L	6.5	28.20	4.8	60.6	4.2	47.6
Orthophosphate	mg P/L	6.1	5.21	17.9	21.2	13.8	18.1
Soluble proteins	mg/g VSS	20.5	23.8	-	-	22.51	30.8
Soluble carbohydrates	mg/g VSS	5.13	7.19	-	-	6.3	12.1
VFA	mg COD/L	-	-	29.63	197.76	14.58	76.55
VFA/sCOD	%	-	-	20.29	32.16	10.96	16.12

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3.2 Structure of Prokaryotic Communities of SS at the phylum level

197 All ASVs detected in this work were assigned to the Bacteria domain. Several earlier studies on
198 sludge yielded comparable outcomes, showing that bacteria constituted nearly the entire prokaryotic
199 population in SS (98.8%), with Archaea accounting for only 1.2% (Yu et al., 2012; Zhang et al., 2012;
200 Xia et al., 2010; McLellan et al., 2010; Mathur et al., 2023). Bacteria are well-adapted to the sewage
201 sludge environments, as many species can survive in aerobic and anaerobic conditions (e.g., through
202 anaerobic respiration or fermentation). In contrast, Archaea are more commonly found in extreme
203 environments, such as strictly anaerobic, very hot, acidic, or saline conditions, like swamps, deep
204 ocean floors, or hot springs (Reed et al., 2013). Specifically, the microbiota structure of the SS
205 samples from F1 and F2 was comparatively analysed considering the relative abundances at the phyla,
206 family, and genus levels. Our analysis demonstrated the presence of a core microbial community and
207 a small variable percentage, primarily considering the phyla level (Figure 2). These slight fluctuations
208 in the composition of the starting SS sample can be justified considering that, although the starting
209 SS samples were collected from the same Oxidic Settling Anaerobic reactor, the samplings were
210 conducted approximately three months apart so the negligible differences can be attributable to the
211 different environmental conditions and temperature, as previously indicated in other reports (Chen et
212 al., 2017).

213 The Proteobacteria, Bacteroidetes, Firmicutes and Verrucomicrobia were identified as the core
214 microbiota in the sludge starting samples (Figure 2), differently from other reports (Yu et al., 2012).

215 In Yu et al., 2012, Actinobacteria were also part of the core microbiota in addition to these phyla. In
216 another case, we detected Chloroflexi at a percentage of 5% (Di Leto et al., 2022) and Chlamydiae at
217 a rate of 4.79% (Mineo et al., 2024), indicating the importance of the microbial analysis of the sewage
218 sludge before the fermentation. The predominant components found in the sewage sludge samples at
219 the beginning of fermentation processes (i.e. T0-F1 and T0-F2) belonged to the Proteobacteria,
220 Bacteroidetes, Verrucomicrobia, Firmicutes, and Acidobacteria phyla.

221 Proteobacteria abundance was 52.11% and 48.64% in T0-F1 and T0-F2, Bacteroidetes 39.19% and
222 41.47%, respectively, Verrucomicrobia 3.34% and 3.59% respectively, and Firmicutes 1.59% and
223 0.81%. These four bacterial phyla are characteristic of the wastewater microbial community.
224 Generally, Proteobacteria and Bacteroidetes are dominant phyla in wastewater treatment plant
225 effluents (Do et al., 2019), and Verrucomicrobia phylum is predominant in soil. It can contribute to
226 carbon cycling in terrestrial ecosystems (Nixon et al., 2019). The Firmicutes, the Bacteroidetes, and
227 Proteobacteria phyla constitute the faecal bacterial community of wastewaters (Scaccia et al., 2020).

228 In specific environmental and pH conditions, Proteobacteria, Bacteroidetes, and Firmicutes are
229 known to be positively related to VFA production in reactors (Atasoy et al., 2022; Swiatkiewicz et
230 al., 2021). High yields of VFA were analysed at a pH of 7.0 ± 0.3 (Swiatkiewicz et al., 2021), and in
231 our study, the initial pH was 7.21 in F1 and 7.15 in F2 (Mineo et al., 2023). This suggests that
232 Proteobacteria, Bacteroidetes, and Firmicutes had favourable conditions to produce VFA. Recent
233 studies underlined the importance of the starting microbial community in influencing the VFA
234 production mechanisms under precise fermentation conditions; it was also highlighted that the
235 dominant phyla were Firmicutes, Bacteroidetes, and Proteobacteria. In particular, the samples
236 yielding the maximum VFA during fermentation were initially composed of Proteobacteria, followed
237 by Bacteroidetes and Firmicutes (Atasoy et al., 2019), as the starting samples of this study. As far as
238 we know, the role of Verrucomicrobia in VFA production is unknown.

239 After fermentation, the most striking difference between the two experiments was the increase of
240 Firmicutes from 0.81% in T0-F2 to 10.54% in TF-F2 compared to T0-F1 (1.59%) and TF-F1 (0.46%).

241 After the fermentation, it was possible to appreciate an increase of different phyla in the two
242 conditions. Bacteroidetes (from 39.19% to 41.65%), Verrucomicrobia (from 3.34% to 4.36%), and
243 Acidobacteria (from 0.75% to 2.26%) increased in TF-F1, whilst Proteobacteria (from 48.64% to
244 59.19%), and Actinobacteria (from 0.29% to 1.97 %) increased in TF- F2. Considering that condition
245 F1 led to a VFA yield of 29.63 mg COD/L with acidogenic fermentation and condition F2 to a higher
246 yield, equal to 197.76 mg COD/L, we can surmise that condition F2 selected VFA-producing

247 microorganisms. In a previous work (Lim et al., 2020) that aimed to optimise the production of VFA
 248 from wastewater, the relevant involvement of Proteobacteria, Firmicutes, and Actinobacteria was
 249 observed. In particular, Firmicutes and Actinobacteria were found to be anaerobic microorganisms
 250 that tolerate the acidic conditions of fermentation to produce VFA (Lim et al., 2020). The mentioned
 251 groups can produce VFA as a product of their biochemical activity. Firmicutes are related to
 252 transforming simple sugars into organic acids, and Actinobacteria can produce propionic acid
 253 (Dworkin et al., 2006). It has been found (Qin et al., 2021) that Firmicutes and Actinobacteria phyla
 254 dominate in the anaerobic digestion of SS or, in any case, at low oxygen concentrations. Therefore,
 255 the 40% headspace, where less oxygen is available, allowed for better adaptation and selection of
 256 VFA-producing bacteria.

257
 258 **Figure 2.** Histograms reporting the composition of samples T0 and TF at the taxonomic level of phyla
 259 (percentage abundance greater than 1%). The relative abundance indicated the percentage of each
 260 phylum compared to all the identified phyla.

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 262 **Taxonomic composition of Proteobacteria at family level**

263 The microbial composition within their respective phyla was studied at the taxonomic family level.
 264 Figure 3 illustrates the microbial composition of Proteobacteria, highlighting the predominant

265 families. In samples T0-F1 and T0-F2, the most prevalent bacterial families were Comamonadaceae
266 (26.78% and 21.10%, respectively), Rhodocyclaceae (18.17% and 14.96%, respectively),
267 Rhodobacteraceae (8.97% and 7.03%, respectively), and Xanthomonadaceae (11.63% and 10.43%,
268 respectively). Additionally, T0-F1 exhibited a notable abundance of Moraxellaceae (12.31%)
269 compared to T0-F2 (5.83%), whereas T0-F2 showed notable abundance of Beijerinckiaceae (12.00%)
270 absent in T0-F1. Notably, the Comamonadaceae family, known for its ability to degrade VFAs for
271 synthesising polyhydroxyalkanoates, was prominent in both conditions (Strazzera et al., 2021).
272 However, their abundance was approximately constant after fermentation in F1 (26.78% in T0, and
273 24.42% in TF), while it dropped from 21.10% to 10.78% in F2. In a previous work that aimed to
274 improve VFA production in batch tests, we found that Comamonadaceae abundance decreased in the
275 sample with the best yield of VFA (Mineo et al., 2024). The reduction of Comamonadaceae, acting
276 as VFA degraders, can explain the enhanced VFA yield in TF-F2. The Rhodocyclaceae family
277 showed the same behaviour: constant in F1 (from 18.17% in T0 and 17.43% in TF) and mainly in
278 TF-F2 (dropping from 14.96% of T0 to zero of TF). Generally, Rhodocyclaceae, being facultative
279 anaerobes, can grow both in the presence and absence of oxygen. However, the greater availability
280 of oxygen, such as in F1, where the headspace volume is higher (60%), favoured the growth of
281 Rhodocyclaceae, compared to F2 (40% headspace). In mixed microbial communities, the response
282 of Rhodocyclaceae to oxygen fluctuations can be complex and influenced by interactions with other
283 microorganisms (Shi et al., 2021).

284 In TF-F1 and TF-F2, there was a notable increase in the Gram-negative acidotolerant family
285 Rhodobacteraceae, increasing from 8.97% in T0-F1 to 13.42% in TF-F1 and from 7.03% in T0-F2 to
286 15.84% in TF-F2. Although their presence has been registered in other studies on waste fermentation
287 for VFA production (Mirmohamadsadeghi et al., 2021), their role could have been better investigated.
288 Also, the abundance of Xanthomonadaceae increased in both experiments: from 11.63% to 18.44%
289 (T0-F1 to TF-F1), and from 10.43% to 16.82% (T0-F2 to TF-F2). This bacterial family was
290 characterised by a metabolism associated with facultative anaerobic fermentation. A distinguishing
291 factor between F1 and F2 is undoubtedly the presence of the Beijerinckiaceae family. In T0-F1 and
292 TF-F1, this family was absent, whereas it constituted 12.00% of T0-F2 and significantly increased to
293 38.35% in TF-F2. The Beijerinckiaceae family is comprised of mesophilic bacteria with optimum
294 growth at 20-40°C. Their absence in sample T0-F1, collected in winter, might be attributed to the
295 colder winter temperatures compared to the mild conditions during the spring when sample T0-F2
296 was taken. While limited research confirms VFA production by Beijerinckiaceae, some family
297 members have been identified in fermenters where VFA production occurred (Khan et al., 2020).
298 This suggests they might have the required enzymatic machinery for fermentative metabolism and

299 could generate VFAs or other organic acids as metabolic byproducts when degrading organic
 300 substrates. Finally, the abundance of Moraxellaceae decreased notably in both experiments during
 301 fermentation, dropping from 12.31% in T0-F1 to 1.85% in TF-F1, and from 5.83% in T0-F2 to 1.03%
 302 in TF-F2. The Moraxellaceae family was found to be related to less production of some VFAs, such
 303 as propionate or butyrate (Miceli et al., 2016). Taking into account all these results and the role of
 304 bacteria in VFA biosynthesis or degradation, this study suggests that a microbial community
 305 characterised by the increase of the Beijerinckiaceae family and the decrease of the Comamonadaceae
 306 family can yield a higher VFA production, as we found in F2. However, more studies on the bacterial
 307 strains are necessary to investigate and exploit their role in VFA production from wastewater.

308

309 **Figure 3.** Pie charts reporting the microbiota structure of samples T0 and TF at the taxonomic level
 310 of the family belonging to Proteobacteria phyla. T0-F1 and T0-F2 represent sewage sludge microbiota
 311 structure at the beginning of the fermentation process in F1 and F2 conditions, respectively; TF-F1
 312 and TF-F2 represent the sewage sludge microbiota structure after fermentation processes. The
 313 relative abundance indicated the percentage of each family compared to all the identified families
 314 belonging to the Proteobacteria phylum.

315

316 **Taxonomic composition of Bacteroidetes at the family level**

317 The predominant families within the Bacteroidetes phylum were Saprospiraceae and
318 Chitinophagaceae, followed by Flavobacteriaceae and Cytophagaceae (Figure 4). Notably, the
319 Cryomorpaceae family is more abundant in T0-F1 and the BA008 family in T0-F2. Saprospiraceae
320 and Chitinophagaceae showed an increase in F1, increasing from 28.37% in T0-F1 to 32.73% in TF-
321 F1 and from 29.36% in T0-F1 to 38.07% in TF-F1, respectively. In contrast, they decreased in F2
322 from 60.53% in T0-F2 to 56.30% in TF-F2 and were similar in F2 (8.88% in T0 and 8.52% in F2).
323 Flavobacteriaceae decreased in F1 (from 17.96% in T0-F1 to 14.22% in TF-F1) and F2 (from 9.68%
324 in T0-F2 to 4.06% in TF-F2). Cytophagaceae declined in F1, dropping from 12.30% in T0-F1 to
325 8.17% in TF-F1, while they increased from 10.49% in T0-F2 to 26.01% in TF-F2. The BA008 family
326 was absent in the initial and final samples of F1. In contrast, they were present in T0-F2 at 6.67% and
327 slightly decreased in TF-F2 to 4.30%. Previous works determined a more significant percentage of
328 Saprospiraceae and Chitinophagaceae in treatments with lower VFA yield (Di Leto et al., 2022).
329 Arguably, members of the Saprospiraceae could significantly break down carbon sources, leading to
330 beneficial carbon substrates for other microorganisms (Johnston et al., 2019). The Saprospiraceae
331 family is commonly found in flocs and aggregates of activated sludge. However, their exact role in
332 wastewater treatment must be better understood (Guo et al., 2016; Guo et al., 2017).

333 Flavobacteriaceae are known primarily as aerobic, Gram-negative bacteria. Although some members
334 of the Flavobacteriaceae family can participate in organic matter degradation, they are not specifically
335 VFA producers, and a decrease in both F1 and F2 samples was registered. The capacity of
336 Cytophagaceae to produce VFA needs to be better understood; however, in our previous studies
337 focused on optimising VFA yield from wastewater, we found Cytophagaceae to be associated with
338 good VFA production (Mineo et al., 2024) Although little information is available on BA008, the
339 only strain isolated so far belonging to this family has an anaerobic fermentative metabolism and
340 could contribute to the production of butyrate (Sun et al. 2016).

341 Altogether, this analysis suggests the main role of Cytophagaceae in VFA production in the tested
342 conditions.

343

344 **Figure 4.** Pie charts report the microbiota structure of samples T0 and TF at the taxonomic level of
 345 the family belonging to the Bacteroidetes phylum. T0-F1 and T0-F2 represent sewage sludge
 346 microbiota structure at the beginning of the fermentation process in F1 and F2 conditions,
 347 respectively; TF-F1 and TF-F2 represent the sewage sludge microbiota structure after fermentation
 348 processes. The relative abundance indicated the percentage of each family compared to all identified
 349 families belonging to the Bacteroidetes phylum.

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351

352 **Taxonomic composition of Verrucomicrobia, Firmicutes and Actinobacteria at family level**

353 The most represented bacterial family for Verrucomicrobia was Verrucomicrobiaceae, which was
 354 equally abundant in both T0-F1 and T0-F2 (79.2%). However, during the fermentation process, the
 355 abundances shifted in opposite directions: in TF-F1, the abundance slightly decreased to 70.2%,
 356 whereas in TF-F2, it increased to 100% (Figure 5). Recent studies validated the role of
 357 Verrucomicrobiaceae in VFA production from xylan, confirming the fermentative capabilities of this
 358 microbial family (Takizawa et al., 2021).

359

360 **Figure 5.** Pie charts reporting the taxonomic composition of samples T0 and TF at the taxonomic
 361 level of the family belonging to Verrucomicrobia phylum. T0-F1 and T0-F2 represent sewage sludge
 362 microbiota structure at the beginning of the fermentation process in F1 and F2 conditions,
 363 respectively; TF-F1 and TF-F2 represent the sewage sludge microbiota structure after fermentation
 364 processes. The relative abundance indicated the percentage of each family compared to all the
 365 identified families belonging to the Verrucomicrobia phylum.

366

367 In our previous studies, Firmicutes were the bacterial phylum most implicated in VFA production
 368 (Mineo et al., 2024 Di Leto et al., 2022). Carnobacteriaceae and Christensenellaceae mainly
 369 represented the Firmicutes phylum (Figure 6). Carnobacteriaceae increased from 46.53% in T0-F1 to
 370 57.28% in TF-F1, absent in T0-F2 and TF-F2. So far, their role has yet to be deeply investigated.
 371 Christensenellaceae family was present at 21.15% in T0-F1 and reached 36.89% in TF-F1 while it
 372 started from 60.95% in T0-F2 and reached 73.04% in TF-F2. While the literature does not recognise
 373 the role of Christensenellaceae in wastewater, this bacterial family, found in the intestinal microbiota,
 374 is known as an excellent producer of acetate and, consequently, an excellent producer of VFA
 375 (Mackei et al., 2022). Other Firmicutes found were Ruminococcaceae and Acidaminobacteraceae,
 376 which decreased at fermentation.

377

378 **Figure 6.** Pie charts reporting the taxonomic composition of samples T0 and TF at the taxonomic
 379 level of family belonging to Firmicutes phylum. T0-F1 and T0-F2 represent sewage sludge
 380 microbiota structure at the beginning of the fermentation process in F1 and F2 condition, respectively;
 381 TF-F1 and TF-F2 represent the sewage sludge microbiota structure after fermentation processes. The
 382 relative abundance indicated the percentage of each family compared to all the identified family
 383 belonging to Firmicutes phylum.

384 Finally, the most representative family belonging to the Actinobacteria phylum were
 385 Intrasporangiaceae, absent in F1 but 40.26% in T0-F2 and increased to 85.82% in TF-F2 (Figure 7).
 386 Intrasporangiaceae are involved in the biological removal of phosphates from wastewater and
 387 bioremediation processes. Some species are fermentative so they may be involved in the
 388 decomposition of organic matter and potentially contribute to the production of VFA (Stackebrandt
 389 et al., 2014). The only family detected in both T0 and TF samples of F1 was C111, for which no
 390 information available was found.

391

392 **Figure 7.** Pie charts reporting the taxonomic composition of samples T0 and TF at the taxonomic
 393 level of family belonging to Actinobacteria phylum. T0-F1 and T0-F2 represent sewage sludge
 394 microbiota structure at the beginning of the fermentation process in F1 and F2 condition, respectively;
 395 TF-F1 and TF-F2 represent the sewage sludge microbiota structure after fermentation processes. The
 396 relative abundance indicated the percentage of each family compared to all identified families
 397 belonging to the Actinobacteria phylum.

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400 3.3 Predicting Microbial Metabolism and oxygen requirement

401

402 Understanding the metabolic functions of the microbiota of each sample can help discover how the
 403 headspace in the fermentation process favoured or penalised VFA production. As shown in Figure 8,
 404 the metabolic activities mainly represented were dehalogenation and ammonia oxidation, followed
 405 by sulfate and nitrite-reducing capabilities. Specifically, there was a high percentage of nitrite
 406 reducers in the TF-F2 sample, which gave the highest VFA yield (13.97%). In the T0-F1 and TF-F1
 407 samples, there was a lower abundance of nitrite-reducers (6.91% and 7.13% respectively) and sulfate-
 408 reducers (13.32% and 12.34% respectively). Dehalogenating bacteria increased in TF-F2 compared
 409 to T0-F2 but remained at a lower percentage than T0-F1 and TF-F1 (18.80% and 18.83%,
 410 respectively). Sulfate-reducing bacteria can oxidize organic matter into acetate and carbon dioxide

411 (Bertolino et al., 2012). Some VFAs such as acetate, propionate, and butyrate are among the most
 412 relevant electron donors to sulfate-reducing bacteria. Indeed, sulfate-reducing bacteria can also use
 413 propionate and butyrate to synthesise acetate, which they then use as a donor for sulfate reduction
 414 (Grigoryan et al., 2008). This work detected acetate during day 8 of fermentation, and no propionic
 415 acid was measured (Mineo et al., 2023), demonstrating acetate production by sulfate-reducing
 416 bacteria. After the peak at day 11, methanogenic activity led to acetate consumption and CO₂
 417 production operated by sulfate-reducing bacteria. VFA are also able to stimulate the
 418 biotransformation of nitrogen (Oguz et al., 2006) through the denitrification of nitric nitrogen to
 419 gaseous nitrogen, and this justifies the presence of metabolic activity of nitrite reducer marked in the
 420 TF-F2 sample in which the VFA concentration is higher. As regards dehalogenation, the relationship
 421 between VFA production and dehalogenation is not well known. What is known is that VFAs act as
 422 electron donors for the dechlorination of chloroethene processes (Lu et al., 2006). The fact that
 423 dehalogenating bacteria were lower in TF-F2 and higher in TF-F1 can justify the different yields of
 424 VFA. The produced VFA were probably used as electron donors by dehalogenating bacteria in greater
 425 abundance in TF-F1 (reducing VFA yields) compared to TF-F2, where there was a lower
 426 concentration of these bacteria. Therefore, it can be assumed that the increase in TF-F2 of the
 427 sulphate-reducers bacteria favours the rise of VFA, particularly acetate, on peak days. Instead, the
 428 increase of nitrite reducers bacteria is favoured by the presence of VFAs. The difference between
 429 sulfate-reducing and dehalogenating bacteria is that the first can produce VFA and then use it as an
 430 electron donor. At the same time, the second directly degrades the VFA produced by other bacteria
 431 as electron donors, reducing VFA yields.
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433

434 **Figure 8.** Putative metabolic requirements of the bacterial microbiota members residing in the
435 samples T0-F1, TF-F1, T0-F2, TF-F2 as inferred by METAGENassist bioinformatic analysis. The
436 abundance percentage of bacteria having a specific metabolism is indicated.

437

438

439 Considering the oxygen requirements (Figure 9) of the microbiota of the four analysed samples,
440 variations were dependent on fermentation and the percentage of the headspace of each experiment.
441 In the F1 experiment, at 60% headspace, there was a higher starting oxygen availability; in the F2
442 fermentation experiment, at 40% headspace, there was a lower starting oxygen availability. During
443 the fermentation process, the starting oxygen rate was further reduced, causing an alteration in the
444 aerobic/anaerobic microbiota ratio. From the beginning of fermentation onwards, there was a
445 reduction in oxygen and an increase in CO₂ (Mineo et al., 2023). Condition F2 promoted anaerobic
446 bacteria's growth and aerobic ones' reduction (Figure S5), thus establishing a VFA-producing factory
447 characterised by acidogenic fermentation when the headspace was 40%.

448

449

450 **Figure 9.** Oxygen requirements of the bacterial microbiota of T0-F1, TF-F1, T0-F2, TF-F2 samples.

451 The abundance percentage of bacteria having a specific metabolism is indicated.

452

453 3.4 Structure of Prokaryotic Communities of SS at genera level

454 Heatmap analysis showed that a 60% headspace volume did not greatly influence the microbiota
455 structure, as the two samples clustered together. Conversely, a 40% headspace volume caused a great
456 variation in the microbial community, as the two samples clustered in two different clade, and led to
457 a higher VFA yield. This result underscores the impact of the headspace volume on the microbial
458 fermentation carried out by bacteria in the sewage sludge.

459 The most representative genera revealed by the metataxonomic analysis are reported in Figure 10.
460 Despite the high number of unclassified, *Rhodobacter* and *Thermomonas* were the most abundant
461 genera in TF-F2 (reaching 4.74 and 4.05%, respectively). *Rhodobacter* was also abundant in TF-F1
462 (4.56%), while *Thermomonas* abundance was detected at a very low level in TF-F1 (1.29%). Both
463 genera were less represented in the starting sewage sludge. Contrarily, *Flavobacterium* and
464 *Dechloromonas* were close to zero in TF-F2.

465 *Rhodobacter*, *Thermomonas* and *Dechloromonas* belong to the Proteobacteria phylum and
466 *Flavobacterium* to Bacteroidetes. It is noteworthy that different headspace volumes selected some
467 bacterial genera that increased or decreased in abundance. In TF-F2, where the initial oxygen
468 availability was lower (40% headspace), more anaerobic genera, such as *Rhodobacter* and
469 *Thermomonas* increased. *Rhodobacter* is known for its ability to degrade VFAs and produce H₂ (Hu
470 et al., 2020). *Thermomonas* is positively correlated with the acidogenic fermentation of sewage sludge
471 and the production of VFA (Kim et al., 2010).

472 Although *Rhodobacter* and *Thermomonas*, known as VFA degraders, increased in TF-F2, the
473 evidence that a better yield of VFA was obtained in TF-F2 could be due to pH. Indeed, Hu et al.
474 (2020) demonstrated that the composition of VFAs produced by the mixed microbial community and
475 a pH between 5.8 and 7.1 can determine the inhibition of the degradation effect of *Rhodobacter*.
476 Given that the initial pH in F2 was 7.15 (Mineo et al., 2023), likely that *Rhodobacter* did not break
477 down the VFAs produced by other bacterial genera. The other explanation could be the presence of
478 VFA producers among the unclassified bacteria.

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4 Conclusions

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SS microbiota subjected to acidogenic fermentation in a pilot plant reactor by modulating the headspace of the reactor was analysed to maximise VFA yield. Two different headspace conditions were evaluated: 60% and 40%. The best VFA yield was obtained after eleven days of fermentation at 40% headspace. Metataxonomic analyses revealed that the lower initial oxygen concentration (due to 40% of headspace) and acidic conditions (due to fermentation) favoured the selection of essentially Gram-negative, anaerobic, and good VFA-producing bacteria. At 60% headspace, there was greater initial oxygen availability, and a greater abundance of VFA-degrading microorganisms was identified. However, several bacterial families identified in this research as potential significant VFA producers were not previously explored for their metabolic capabilities in wastewater or other organic-rich environments. Consequently, this study should stimulate in-depth investigations into these bacteria and their role in acidogenic fermentation and VFA production, aiming towards biotechnological and industrial applications in the future. This work also demonstrates how the wastewater of Unipa Campus can be used, according to the idea of circular economy, to produce valuable material to improve bioplastic production and their precursor, reducing waste disposal and

510 environmental impact. Thus, by optimizing the production of VFA to be used in the PHA production
511 process, a transition from linear wastewater treatment to circular biorefineries can be promoted at the
512 campus level. In addition, from a circular economy perspective, the purified wastewater from the
513 Unipa Campus could be repurposed to irrigate green spaces and clean campus streets.

514

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519

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